

Sepide Taheri, Nahid Atghia, **Maryam Mokhtari Dinani**. (2018). [Relationship between Leadership Style and Job Stress in Personnel of the Administration of Sport and Youth Kurdistan Province](#), *Strategic Studies on Youth and Sports*, 17(39):1- 21.

Relationship between Leadership Style and Job Stress in Personnel of the Administration of Sport and Youth Kurdistan Province

Sepide Taheri

Master Degree in Sport Management, Alzahra University, Tehran, Iran

Nahid Atghia

Ph.D., Assistant Professor of Sport Management Department, Alzahra University, Tehran, Iran

Maryam Mokhtari Dinani¹

Ph.D., Assistant Professor of Sport Management Department, Alzahra University, Tehran, Iran

Abstract: The research is to study the relationship between Leadership style and Job Stress in personnel of the administration of sport and youth in Kurdistan province. The population was all personnel of the administration of sport and youth in Kurdistan province that was selected as the total number of samples to this research. Two research made questionnaires were used to collect the data. Formal and content validity of both questionnaires were approved by 11 professors and experts in the field of sport management. Also, construct validity was approved through principal components analysis method. However, in a pilot study, Cronbach's alpha coefficient of leadership style questionnaire was assessed 0.90 and Cronbach's alpha coefficient of job stress questionnaire was approved 0.86. Data analysis was performed by Pearson correlation and Multivariate regression. The results of Pearson correlation analysis showed that only Participative and Supportive leadership styles had negative correlation with job stress ($p < 0.05$). Also, results of Multivariate regression analysis showed that Participative, Supportive and Autocratic leadership styles had the most prediction capability for job stress respectively. Thus, it is important to notice to leadership style in sport work place by sport managers specially Supportive and Participative leadership style as an effective factor can decrease the Job Stress.

Key Words: Leadership Style, Job Stress, Personnel, Administration of Sport and Youth, and Kurdistan Province

¹. Assistant Professor of Alzahra University, Email: M.mokhtaridinani@alzahra.ac.ir